

ISSUES OF TEACHING PHONETICS AT A TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY

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Annotation: This article discusses some issues of teaching phonetics in a non-linguistic university. Some methods of teaching foreign language pronunciation are described. An original non-traditional approach to explaining the articulation of English sounds based on a comparison of the articulation of English and Russian sounds is considered. The article can be used by both English teachers and those who study English on their own.

Key words: phonetics of the English and Russian languages, comparisons, techniques and teaching methods, native language, phrasal stress, elision.

Talking and arguing about the importance of mastering English by students of engineering specialties is “a thing of bygone days”. And the reason is not even that knowledge of foreign languages raises the general cultural level, broadens one's horizons, and expands one's worldview. This is already so obvious that it is not discussed. “The general social significance of the humanitarian component of a graduate of a technical university is determined by the modern vision of the future development of mankind, where the main parameters will be determined not so much by technology as by the level of culture of each member of society”

Knowing a foreign language, and especially English, is important for purely practical purposes - to be at the forefront of solving engineering and technical problems, at the forefront of scientific goals and topical scientific and technical problems of modern civilization. And in the modern labor market, engineers who speak foreign languages are much more in demand. If twenty-thirty years ago, future engineers in our country were faced with such tasks as: being able to read specialized literature in a foreign language in order to be aware of the innovative developments of their foreign colleagues, but now, in the era of globalization, the goals have changed, more precisely, they have expanded.

Scientists and engineers from different countries must work together to solve not only scientific and technical problems that improve and improve our lives, but global problems facing humanity - to put a barrier to international terrorism, to protect our common home - planet Earth - from external space threats, to find alternative energy sources, solve global environmental problems, etc.

If a few decades ago the main task of foreign language teachers was to develop students' reading skills, now communicative competence has come to the fore - or (in terms of speech activity) speaking and listening, since they provide communication, and, therefore, influence to achieve success in international cooperation. Hence, phonetics acquires colossal importance, and it is important not only to master pronunciation skills in order to be understood by others, but it is equally (if not more!) important to teach and learn to understand foreign language speech of your foreign colleagues, since only knowledge of the norm helps to develop prediction, which is extremely important for understanding foreign speech by ear. In this article, I would like to focus on some principles teaching phonetics at a technical university. In the conditions of a technical university, where the time for teaching a foreign language is limited, phonetics as a subject is not specially singled out. Therefore, it is necessary to focus only on the most difficult sounds, although the very concept of “difficult sounds” is ephemeral.

Based on my personal teaching experience of phonetics for twenty years, I concluded that these include both sounds that do not exist in the native language, for example, [ə, ð, ə:], and those that are very close in sound to the sounds of the native language, for example, most vowel sounds, but have certain differences.

I am convinced that the phonetics of the native language should be the starting point for teaching foreign pronunciation. My experience has proven the truth of this statement. It is necessary to find similar consonances in the native language. S.I. spoke about this back in 1975. Bernstein in his article "Issues of teaching pronunciation": "... the articulation of a foreign language should be studied in constant correlation with the pronunciation skills of the native speech." N.D. Lukina in her "Introductory Remedial Course of the English Language" and previous works gave many excellent examples, one of which is how, for example, to learn to pronounce the word "look". N.D. Lukina in her "Introductory Remedial Course of the English Language" and previous works gave many excellent examples, one of which is how, for example, to learn to pronounce the word "look".

To do this, you need to build a chain of such words: "bow - look - hatch". In this chain, the English word "look" occupies a middle, intermediate position between the words from the Russian language "bow" and "hatch". There are many similar examples in Russian and English: "sam - some" (to emphasize the difference in the initial sounds in this pair); "chip - fish" (to determine the difference between Russian and English vowels), etc. Thus, in order to achieve the result and, what is very important, for self-examination, it is very effective to build an opposition of close sounds, Russian and English, and offer to "feel the difference". An example of another similar opposition is the Russian "e" and [e] English, before pronouncing words such as "bed", "left", etc. Similarly, when learning the correct pronunciation of the diphthong [ɛə] in such frequently used words like "parents" or "careful" and others. Ask students to first say "ea" in Russian and then [ɛə] in English. The effect is so striking that after a few lessons, almost all students master this diphthong, one of the most difficult for Russian-speaking people. This is due to the fact that students start from their native sound and, by establishing the difference between similar sounds in their native and English languages, they can control this difference themselves. Since it is no secret that the slow success in mastering foreign phonetics by adult students is due precisely to the fact that it is difficult for them to assess how correctly or incorrectly they pronounce when they do their homework, that is, in the absence of a teacher who is ready to correct mistakes. Having at your disposal the opposition of the sounds of the native and foreign languages and feeling the difference between them, it is much easier to master the skills of a foreign language pronunciation even without a consultant teacher.

When working on phonetic material, I believe that one should not be smart and delve into the classification of sounds, puzzle students, future engineers, with such terms as back-lingual sound, front row sound, fricative sounds, etc. It is very important, in my opinion, to find such an explanation, such a comparison, which will naturally lead students to the correct pronunciation of the sound. So, when explaining the sound [ɑ:] one can tell students that they should know that "the vowel [ɑ:] is a deep, long, open sound.[2]

When pronouncing it, the tongue is pulled back as much as possible as for (O), the back of the tongue is only slightly raised above the rest of it, the jaw is lowered. You should not, however, lower the jaw too low, otherwise the vowel will not be deep enough and turn into "a", or you

can ask them to remember how crows croak (may the phoneticians of language universities forgive me), but the effect is achieved (!). When explaining the sound [ʃ]: instead of long instructions on how to raise the middle part of the tongue, where the tip of the tongue should be, ask students to add a soft sign to the Russian sound “sh”, and again you will get the desired result. If we remember how children lisp at the age of 3, and pronounce in their manner the well-known phrase “Sasha walked along the highway and sucked dry”, we get a wonderful English sound [s]. Students make many mistakes at the intersection of words, where, for example, there should be a loss of explosion, as in: “point ten”, “ask Catherine”, “What can I do?” It is enough to find such words or phrases in the native Russian language, where there would be similar sound combinations, for these examples - as in the words “from there” or “because”, respectively (note that in Russian they are easily pronounced with the loss of an explosion). And, before training the loss of an explosion at the junction of English words, ask students to pronounce these familiar words from the Russian language, drawing their (students') attention to the necessary sound combinations. After such an exercise, students cope with this phonetic phenomenon in English much faster and easier.[3]

Phrasal stress is of great importance. Phrasal stress means that there are stressed and unstressed words in a sentence, and that unstressed words, like unstressed syllables, are reduced. And reduction can be different: in terms of quantity and quality, i.e. reduction can lead to a change not only in the length of the sound, but also in the replacement of one sound by another, or in elision, i.e., the loss of a sound or sounds.[4]

Take, for example, the pronunciation of the phrase “there is”. For almost 40 years of work at MSTU. N.E. Bauman, I don't remember a case when any of the students pronounced it the way it is pronounced by native speakers in the overwhelming majority of cases, namely [ðeəz]. Ignorance of the pronunciation form of this turnover makes it difficult to understand authentic English speech by ear. Here is another striking example: the phrase “tell him” is pronounced [tel im], and the phrase tell her is pronounced [tel ə]. It is very important for students to know such features of reduction and elision, and in particular, reduction and elision of these phrases. In addition, it is also necessary to develop the skill of pronouncing these very frequently used phrases, because ignorance of these features and lack of skill can lead to misunderstanding of foreign speech, i.e. the act of communication may not take place and / or have inadequate consequences.

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Another example to which I would like to draw the attention of English teachers. To reduce the difficulties of listening to authentic English speech, it is necessary to get acquainted with another common case associated with the reduction of unstressed auxiliary verbs in combination with modal verbs in phrases: should have been, may have done, must have been/done, etc. Neither the modal verbs nor the verb “have” in the above and similar phrases

are stressed, and therefore are pronounced like this: [ʃud əv bi:n, mei əv dʌn, məst əv bi:n]. Having the right pronunciation skills, in particular, these phrases, we take another step towards success in a more complete understanding of foreign language speech.

For a speaker of any language, especially for an educated person, diction, the distinctness of pronunciation, is of great importance. To achieve good results in phonetic practice, I motivate my students like this: "You get a good education, which means that sooner or later you will definitely become a leader of one level or another. It is important for a leader to be able to speak well, not only from the point of view of vocabulary and grammar, but also from the point of view of phonetics: distinctly, clearly. The leader needs to be willing to listen. That's the only way to convince." Diction can be trained. You can start with tongue twisters, even with Russian ones, gradually complicating them and moving on to foreign languages, English in this case. By the way, students willingly and enthusiastically perform such exercises, and they themselves find new and exciting tongue twisters. An example of such enthusiasm and enthusiasm in the classroom is the tongue twister (by the way, brought by a student to the audience): "The nervous constitutionalist was found acclimatized in Constantinople." [6]

Intonation. According to Peter Roach, one of the famous modern English phoneticians, intonation cannot be taught in isolation from the language environment. It's hard to argue with that. Tones such as fall-rise seem unnatural, especially to Russian-speaking students. "Singing intonations" of the most common phrases, for example, intonations of gratitude, greetings, appear to students as false. Especially for young men, young men, it seems almost humiliating to use such intonations. In addition, many believe that if there are such intonations, then only in "old-fashioned prim" England. I remember a case from practice. The students did not believe not only me, but also those authentic audio recordings that I gave them to listen to. So one day it happened that they participated in an international youth conference dedicated to astronautics. At this conference, among the participants were Americans, Australians, Indians and representatives of several other countries. My students decided to take with them some of the texts, the recordings of which caused those doubts, and asked the conference participants from the USA, Australia and India to record the reading of these tests on tape. What was their surprise! Returning from the conference, they vied with each other to tell me about the "deed". The intonations of the American student reading the text matched 100 percent with the English notes, the Australian was close to 100 percent, and the Indian read in some places with different intonations from the English. I dare say that after that conference, the teaching of intonation patterns went faster, and it was no longer necessary to convince the students of that group that all native speakers use such intonations. [7]

Another aspect, the importance of which must be taught to students, is the length of the sound. Everyone who learns English from the very beginning knows about the existence of long and short vowels in it. Failure to comply with this rule can lead to embarrassment and even indecent situations. Therefore, I always warn students that the word "beach" is pronounced with a long vowel [i:] . And here is another case from practice, when one of my listeners, a high-ranking head of one of the Russian companies, after discussing the contract with his American colleague, said the phrase "Take this sheet yourself" with a short sound in the third word. Good thing they both have a sense of humor. After that, that leader agreed with me that it is important to observe the length of sounds in English! [8]

And the last, perhaps the most important thing. When you teach adult students who have a “rich” experience of speaking (usually with serious phonetic errors) in a foreign language, you encounter a problem when it seems to students that phonetics is not an obligatory aspect, they are already understood (as it happened in the group of students described above). To some extent this is true. But, firstly, they do not always understand, and, secondly, the competent speech of a well-educated person has not bothered anyone yet.

Self-confidence of students leads to the fact that “the teacher has to overcome quite significant obstacles of a psychological nature and conduct extensive “explanatory work” among students (S.I. Bernshtein). Success in this matter can be ensured by mastery of psychological and pedagogical techniques designed to motivate students, but this is a topic for another article. [9]

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